

Efficacy study of Captopril on some liver function tests in hypertensive patients

Estudio de eficacia de Captopril en algunas pruebas de función hepática en pacientes hipertensos

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142

Abstract

Background: Drug-related liver injury has emerged as a significant public health issue, accounting for more than 50% of instances of acute liver failure.

Objective: to assess, in relation to patient age, dosage, and duration of captopril usage, the impact of captopril monotherapy on a few liver function tests in hypertensive patients.

Subject & Methods: From June 15, 2022, to December 15, 2022, this case control study was conducted in the Internal Medicine Consultation Clinic at the AL-Nasseriya Teaching Hospital in the city of AL-Nasseriya. "Eighty individuals (40 men and 40 women) with mild to moderate primary hypertension who were free of diabetes, liver disease, and other chronic illnesses were divided into two groups: The first group was made up of 45 patients, aged 37 to 60, who had been taking captopril for more than three months. 45 newly discovered, untreated hypertension patients made up the second group, which was matched with the first group in terms of age, sex, and BM". All blood samples from study participants were used to extract serum, which was subsequently used to evaluate different liver function tests using readily available commercial test kits. A sphygmomanometer was used to measure blood pressure (BP) while the subject was seated, and a BMI was generated by dividing the

subject's weight in kilograms by their height in meters».

Results: The captopril group had considerably lower systolic and diastolic blood pressure than the control group. The captopril group considerably outperformed the control group in terms of serum alkaline phosphatase activity (ALP), but differences in the outcomes of the other liver function tests were not statistically significant. The findings of the liver function tests did not significantly differ according to the age of captopril users. There was no observable effect of captopril dose and captopril treatment duration on the liver function tests other from a significant increase in blood ALP with increasing captopril dosage.

Conclusion: The use of captopril medication causes a smooth decrease of blood pressure with no effects on liver function tests, with the exception of a considerably higher level of serum ALP in comparison to the control group and an increase in captopril dose that results in a rise in the serum ALP level. The findings of the liver function tests were unaffected by the age of the patients or the duration of captopril use.

Key words: Captopril, hypertensive patients, liver enzymes.

Resumen

Antecedentes: la lesión hepática relacionada con fármacos se ha convertido en un importante problema de salud pública y representa más del 50 % de los casos de insuficiencia hepática aguda.

Objetivo: evaluar, en relación con la edad del paciente, la dosis y la duración del uso de captopril, el impacto de la monoterapia con captopril en algunas pruebas de función hepática en pacientes hipertensos.

Sujeto y métodos: Del 15 de junio de 2022 al 15 de diciembre de 2022, este estudio de casos y controles se llevó a cabo en la Clínica de Consulta de Medicina Interna del Hospital Universitario AL-Nasseriya en la ciudad de AL-Nasseriya. "Ochenta personas (40 hombres y

40 mujeres) con hipertensión primaria leve a moderada que no padecían diabetes, enfermedad hepática y otras enfermedades crónicas se dividieron en dos grupos: el primer grupo estaba formado por 45 pacientes, de 37 a 60 años, que habían estado tomando captopril durante más de tres meses. 45 pacientes con hipertensión recién descubiertos y no tratados conformaron el segundo grupo, que fue emparejado con el primer grupo en términos de edad, sexo y BM". Todas las muestras de sangre de los participantes del estudio se usaron para extraer suero, que posteriormente se usó para evaluar diferentes pruebas de función hepática utilizando kits de prueba comerciales fácilmente disponibles. Se utilizó un esfigmomanómetro para medir la presión arterial (PA)